

Data and Tools List

One of the goals of the NC RISCC is to synthesize science and share knowledge. We created this list that contains descriptions of and links to existing data, decision tools, and other resources that are related to invasive species and/or climate change in one centralized location. This is a living document that will be updated regularly so please let us know if there are other useful resources that we should add to the list.

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Grassland Productivity Forecast (Grass-Cast)

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Tool that predicts what pasture/grassland productivity will be in the current growing season, based on current and predicted weather, relative to each county's 34-year history for below, normal, or above average future precipitation. Created as a tool for rangeland managers.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2017 - Present
- **Spatial:** Great Plains region (parts of MT, WY, CO, NM, TX, OK, KS, NE, SD, ND, MN)

Contact: Dannele E. Peck (dannele.peck@usda.gov)

Notes: Decision support tool

Figure:

GrassCast prediction for the Great Plains on July 8th 2025. For the 3 maps (scenarios) above: "If precipitation between now and August 31st is above (left map), near (middle), or below (right) normal, we estimate that grassland production in your area (at lbs / acre of peak biomass) will be ____ % more or less than its 36-year average."

Fuelcast

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Tool that provides monthly rangeland fuel loads and vegetation production forecasts during the growing season as well as historical fuel conditions in rangelands and pastures and deviation of the current from historical fuel loads. Can separate total vegetation production and herbaceous (annual and perennial) production.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2000 - Present
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US rangelands and pastures only

Contact: Matt Reeves (matt.c.reeves@usda.gov)

Notes: Primarily for live production but also has information on standing dead fuels and has fuel models as well. Created for rangeland managers and fire managers.

Figure:

Fuelcast current season total vegetation production deviation in pounds per acre (PPA). (Left) Map of current season PPA percent deviation. (Middle) scale for map. (Right) Mean PPA between 2000-2023.

Early Detection and Distribution Mapping System (EDDMapS) Range Shift Listing Tool

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Climate** ▾

Function: Tool provides lists of invasive plants expected to expand their ranges into the chosen county or state with climate change by 2040-2060 based on 13 future climate models.

Extent

- **Temporal:** predictions for 2040-2060
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US

Contact: Chuck Bargereon (bugwood@uga.edu)

Notes: Prevention or management, current and future conditions. Contain only species that are already present in the contiguous United States.

Figure:

Invasive Range Expanders Listing Tool for generating list of possible future invaders in Colorado (CO), based on species presence in adjacent states, and climate suitability based on 13 future climate models.

[Invasive Species Habitat Tool \(INHABIT\)](#)

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Future Predictions** ▾

Function: Web application developed by USGS that analyzes and depicts habitat suitability for over 200 invasive species (non-native, terrestrial and aquatic plants). Maps of habitat suitability are based upon a suite of species distribution models and may be used to identify locations where invasion is most likely. Users may also export a list of potential invaders for a given management unit. INHABIT is an active project with many future extensions planned.

Extent

- **Temporal:** current habitat suitability
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US

Contact: Catherine Jarnevich (gs-fort_iss_inhabit@usgs.gov)

Notes: Current and future conditions, decision support (e.g., prioritizing locations for early detection efforts, lists of potential invaders for a given management unit)

Figure:

INHABIT map for the habitat suitability of Sorghum halepense (Johnsongrass). Color scale (purple to yellow) indicates low to high habitat suitability for Johnsongrass in the region of the interest. Polygon outlined in red dashes represents the current distribution of Johnsongrass based on actual observations.

National Land Cover Database

See *Exotic Annual Grasses*

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** **Invasive Species**

Function: Nationwide database on land cover and land cover change. Useful for mapping Cheatgrass and other invasive grasses.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2021 - 2024
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US (30 m resolution)

Contact: Multi-resolution Land Characteristics Consortium. USGS.
(custserv@usgs.gov)

Notes: Complements the joint [NISC/WFLC Fire and Invasive Species task team](#) and [WGA's "Toolkit"](#).

Figure:

MRLC NLCD Exotic Annual Grass (EAG) product. Users can download percent cover (yellow/green/red) and confidence level (white/blue) maps for EAG.

SIREN

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: Online portal that will incorporate different datasets, risk assessments, horizon scanning, SDMs to assist management. Siren is inclusive of invasive terrestrial, aquatic, and marine taxa within a national scope (including US Territories), and contains tools that are scalable to county, state, regional and user-defined geographic areas.

Extent

- **Spatial:** Continental US and territories

Contact: Amy Wray (USGS); awray@usgs.gov; Brian Reichert (USGS): breichert@usgs.gov; Aimee Agnew (USGS): aagnew@usgs.gov; Nicole D Hernandez (USGS): nhernandez@usgs.gov

Notes: Prevention or management, current and future conditions.

Figure:

SIREN (BETA) species observation map for Bromus inermis (smooth brome). SIREN also has Hotspot Analyses and Horizon Scan information (right panel) that is currently in development.

Nonindigenous Aquatic Species (NAS)

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: Tool provides spatially referenced biogeographic accounts of introduced aquatic species. The website provides scientific reports, real-time queries, spatial data sets, distribution maps, fact sheets, and more on nonindigenous aquatic species.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1800 - present
- **Spatial:** Continental US, Puerto Rico, Virgin Islands, and Guam

Contact: Wesley Daniel (USGS): wdaniel@usgs.gov; Matthew Neilson (USGS): mneilson@usgs.gov; Ian Pfingsten (USGS): ipfingsten@usgs.gov; Kristen Reaver (USGS): kreaver@contractor.usgs.gov

Notes: Management, current conditions.

Figure:

NAS record output for *Dreissena polymorpha* (zebra mussel). Left: distribution map of all observations. Right: associated data table with record information.

Natural Heritage Map Viewer

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Mapping tool to see available data across the state of Montana. Data available includes: species observations, predicted habitat suitability for biodiversity (split by native & invasive), land cover, wetland & riparian maps, land management, biological reports and EPA docs, and photos from site surveys.

Extent

- **Temporal:** Present
- **Spatial:** Montana

Contact: Bryce Maxwell (Montana Heritage Society): bmaxell@mt.gov

Notes: Management, current conditions.

Figure:

Map viewer for noxious weed biodiversity (yellow = high, purple = low). The map viewer allows the user to add a variety of relevant layers into the map, including land management regions and important plant and bird areas.

[Fire and Invasives Assessment Tool \(FIAT\)](#)

Topics: [Invasive Species](#) [Vegetation Cover](#)

Function: BLM product (collection of datasets and reports from a standardized assessment protocol) to show changes in sage-grouse habitat due to wildfire, conifer expansion, and annual invasive grasses.

Extent

- **Temporal:** various dates (2015-2024), not continuous or regular updates
- **Spatial:** 5 different regions in the western US that cover sage-grouse habitat

Contact: Fire Resource Data Liaison: pdelpizzo@blm.gov

Notes: Management, current and historical conditions

Figure:

FIAT data portal that enables the user to search for a variety of data. Users can select Geodatabases or reports, and filter based on the category, geographic region, and data source.

Fire Weather/fuels and fire danger Outlooks

Topics: Climate ▾

Function: Provides daily, 7-day, and monthly fire weather predictions for regions of the U.S.

Extent

- **Spatial:** Contiguous US, Hawaii, ALaska, Puerto Rico and Virgin Islands

Contact: Email: blm_fa_intell@blm.gov; NICC Intelligence: 208-387-5093; Main Line (24 hours): 208-387-5400

Notes: Management, current and historical conditions

Figure:

One of the products offered by NICC: 7-Day Significant Fire Potential map for Thursday, July 31, 2025.

Rangeland Analysis Platform (RAP)

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Maps vegetation cover for the contiguous United States, based upon a machine learning tool incorporating satellite imagery and field data. Many different layers including: percent cover/biomass/net primary productivity for broad categories of vegetation (including annual forb & grass).

Extent

- **Temporal:** annual from 1986 - present; biomass products at 16-day interval
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US at 30 m resolution

Contact: Sarah McCord (USDA): sarah.mccord@usda.gov

Notes: Management, current and historical conditions

Figure:

RAP biomass of annual forbs & grass for 2024. Colored by lbs/acre, darker colors indicate higher biomass.

Rangeland Analysis Platform - Partner Tools

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾ **Future Predictions** ▾

Function: Additional tools based on RAP for particular applications including: cheatgrass extent, rangeland vulnerability to tree encroachment, ecosystem resilience to cheatgrass invasion, and Great Basin fire probability.

Extent

- **Temporal:** variable
- **Spatial:** variable

Contact: See each product for contact information

Notes: Current conditions; historic conditions; future risk

Figure:

'Cheatgrass' app showing early warning for woody transitions (2020) in the Great Plains biome.

Climate Change Vulnerability Index

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Climate** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾
Future Predictions ▾

Function: A tool for evaluating climate change vulnerability of plant and animal species.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US

Contact: Nature Serve: DataSupport@natureserve.org

Notes: Version 4.0, other versions available. Downloadable workbook.

Figure:

CCVI 4.0 algorithm for determining the climate vulnerability of a particular species. Species are categorized into Less Vulnerable (light green), Moderately Vulnerable (light yellow), Highly Vulnerable (dark yellow), Extremely Vulnerable (burnt orange), or Insufficient Evidence (grey).

Climate Portal Guide

Topics: Climate ▾ Future Predictions ▾

Function: A guide that links to various climate change portals (for visualization and data download) and climate assessments. The goal of this guide is to help people find and use resources related to climate change.

Extent

- **Temporal:** variable
- **Spatial:** Mountain west US focused, but varies by individual resource.

Contact: Aspen Global Change Institute (AGCI); Julie Vano (jvano@agci.org); Jeff Lukas (jeff@lukasclimate.com)

Figure:

Climate change portals and related resources

Climate change portals and resources directory.

Climate Voyager (NOT ACTIVE)

Topics: Climate Future Predictions

Function: Provides maps of future climate using temperature and precipitation as predictors. Shows predictions in 20-year windows through the year 2100 for carbon emission scenarios.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US

Contact: Heather Dinon Aldridge, Corey Davis, and Dr. Ryan Boyle at NC state University: voyager@climate.ncsu.edu

Notes: No longer an active tool. Offers links to similar tools.

Figure:

CLIMATE MAPPER
National and regional maps of historical conditions and future climate projections

FUTURE HARDINESS ZONES
Maps of future projections of changes to the USDA's Plant Hardiness Zone regions

FUTURE CLIMATE ANALOGS
Maps of areas with an expected similar historical and future climate conditions

FUTURE BOXPLOTS
Graphs of local projections for several future time slices, as in Climate Voyager

FUTURE TIME SERIES
Graphs of local seasonal projections using different future emissions scenarios

DATA DOWNLOAD
Download historical climate data and future projections for a selected location

Climate Voyager is no longer active but offers links to the above tools.

Resilient Land Mapping Tool

Topics: Climate Future Predictions

Function: Provides maps of resilient and connected lands across continental US. Provides scores for climate change resilience, landscape connectedness, and biodiversity.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** United States

Contact: crccs@tnc.org

Notes: Management, current conditions, future resilience.

Figure:

Resilient Land Mapping Tool for terrestrial resilience which estimates the capacity to maintain species diversity and ecological function as the climate changes.

Seedlot Selection Tool

Topics: **Climate** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾ **Future Predictions** ▾

Function: The Seedlot Selection Tool (SST) is a GIS mapping program designed to help forest managers match seedlots with planting sites based on climatic information. The climates of the planting sites can be chosen to represent current climates, or future climates based on selected climate change scenarios.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1961 - 2100
- **Spatial:** North America

Contact: Dr. Brad St.Clair (USFS): bstclair@fs.fed.us. Nikolas Stevenson-Molnar (Oregon State, Conservation Biology Institute): nik.molnar@consbio.org.

Notes: Management or restoration, current and future conditions.

Figure:

SST seedlot locator for a planned planting in western Alabama. Yellow - red scale indicates regions to look for seedlots in for plant adapted to 2071 - 2100 under the RCP8.5 emission model. White oak range overlaid in purple.

PhenoSynth

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: An open source tool to visualize and interact with phenological data across multiple sources: National Phenology Network, PhenoCam, and remote sensing (MODIS).

Extent

- **Temporal:** ~2008 - present
- **Spatial:** most observations are from North America, but some worldwide.

Contact: Katharyn Duffy: katharyn.duffy@nau.edu; Andrew Richardson: Andrew.Richardson@nau.edu

Notes: This app relies on the R package *rgdal*. This has since been deprecated in CRAN, so you will need to run R version 3.5 or earlier. R shiny app;
Associated article: <https://research.fs.usda.gov/treesearch/63160>

Figure:

PhenoSynth R Shiny app for viewing phenocam locations.

PhenoCam

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: The PhenoCam Network is a cooperative continental-scale phenological observatory that uses imagery from networked digital cameras to track vegetation phenology in a diverse range of ecosystems across North America and around the World. Images and extracted vegetation greenness available in real time on their website.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2008 - present
- **Spatial:** Worldwide

Contact: General help email: phenocam@nau.edu; Andrew Richardson: Andrew.Richardson@nau.edu

Notes: R packages to access data:
<https://github.com/bluegreen-labs/phenocamr> and
<https://github.com/bluegreen-labs/phenor/>

Figure:

Phenocam images from Niwot Ridge LTER taken at 0730 from the [NEON tower top](#). (Left) January 10th 2025. (Right) June 30th 2025.

Early Estimates of Exotic Annual Grass (EAG) in the Sagebrush Biome, USA

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Datasets provide early estimates of 2020-2025 fractional cover for exotic annual grass (EAG) species and one native perennial grass species. Includes fractional cover maps along with their corresponding confidence maps for: 1) a group of 16 species of EAGs, 2) cheatgrass (*Bromus tectorum*); 3) medusahead (*Taeniatherum caput-medusae*); and 4) Sandberg bluegrass (*Poa secunda*).

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2020-2025 on a bi-weekly basis from May to early July
- **Spatial:** Western US (Washington, Oregon, California, Nevada, Arizona, Utah, Idaho, parts of Montana, parts of Wyoming)

Contact: Devendra Dahal: ddahal@contractor.usgs.gov

Notes: Datasets for early estimate/early detection

Figure:

Early estimates of Exotic Annual Grasses (EAG) for May 2025.

Database of invasive annual grass spatial products for the western United States January 2010 to February 2021

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Inventory of spatial products released over the past decade that map cheatgrass, medusahead, and Ventenata within the western U.S. at regional and national scales. Database available as a filterable excel file.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2010 - 2021
- **Spatial:** Contiguous US

Contact: Jessica E Shyvers: jess.shyvers@tnc.org

Notes: Article describing data:

<https://www.usgs.gov/centers/fort-collins-science-center/science/invasive-annual-grass-iag-spatial-dataset-compilation>

Figure:

The USGS collected and summarized 23 spatial datasets:

Product Name	Species of Grass	Recentness	Access the Data
INHABIT Cheatgrass Suitability (2019)	Cheatgrass (<i>Bromus tectorum</i>)	2020	Viewer Data
INHABIT Medusahead Suitability (2019)	Medusahead (<i>Taeniatherum caput-medusae</i>)	2020	Viewer Data
INHABIT Ventenata Suitability (2019)	Ventenata (<i>Ventenata dubia</i>)	2020	Viewer Data
RAP Annual Herbaceous Cover Time series (1984-2019)	Annual herbaceous species	1984-2019	Viewer Data
RAP Annual Herbaceous Biomass Time Series (1986-2019)	Annual herbaceous species	1984-2019	Viewer Data

Subset of the 23 invasive annual grass datasets included in this data product.

CABI Compendium

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: Global database of invasive species.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** Global

Contact: By filling this form: [Contact us | CABI Digital Library](#)

Notes: Detailed coverage of invasive species threatening livelihoods and the environment worldwide.

Figure:

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 | 16 December 2024

Azadirachta indica (neem tree)

Author: [Petra Bakewell-Stone](#) | [AUTHORS INFO & AFFILIATIONS](#)

Publication: CABI Compendium • 8112 • <https://doi.org/10.1079/cabicompendium.8112>

Datasheet Types: Invasive species, Tree, Host plant, Pest

 30,913

 [PDF/EPUB](#)

Abstract

This datasheet on *Azadirachta indica* covers Identity, Overview, Associated Diseases, Pests or Pathogens, Distribution, Dispersal, Hosts/Species Affected, Diagnosis, Biology & Ecology, Environmental Requirements, Natural Enemies, Impacts, Uses, Prevention/Control, Management, Genetics and Breeding, Economics and Further Information.

Example entry on the CABI database for the neem tree.

Global Plant Invaders Database

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: A list of invasive plant taxa, based upon peer-reviewed literature. Authors reviewed literature from 1959 to 2020 and extracted names of plants documented as invasives, resulting in a list of more than 3000 invasive plants with associated taxonomic information.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1959 - 2020
- **Spatial:** Global

Contact: Bethany A. Bradley: bbradley@eco.umass.edu

Figure:

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J	K	L	M	N	O	P	Q	R	S
1	paperid	GPI_name	inv_ctry	explicit_invdef	explicit_invdefdesc	implicit_invdef	implicit_invdefdesc	locdata	locdata_type	finding									
2	AARS1981	hypochoeris radicata	NA	N	NA	NA	NA	N	NA										
3	ABBA2012	spartina densiflora	Spain	N	NA	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	this study showed the ability of the invasive cordgrass s. densiflora to germinate and establish in per									
4	ABBA2020	matia parviflora	Egypt	N	NA	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	in view of our results, goat grazing can be applied as a useful method to control s. halapense and m.									
5	ABBA2020	sorghum halepense	Egypt	N	NA	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	in view of our results, goat grazing can be applied as a useful method to control s. halepense and m.									
6	ABBO2006	peganum harmala	United States of Y		dominates the areas it is introduced	NA	NA	N	NA	african rue grass can tolerate extreme conditions (lack of water, and herbicide application) much be									
7	ABBO2007	peganum harmala	United States of Y		produces allelopathic chemicals in t	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	p. harmala shoot growth is from march to june, and senesced in june and july. only fruit maturation									
8	ABBO2008	peganum harmala	United States of Y		NA	NA	NA	N	NA	the success of african rue in arid environments is due in part to the ability of seedlings to tolerate ani									
9	ABE2011	casuarina equisetifolia	Japan	N	NA	NA	NA	Y	BOTH	our surveys indicate that vegetation cover by the alien tree, casuarina equisetifolia has expanded cor									
10	ABEL2011A	cirsiium arvense	United States of Y		plant invasion is an important probl	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	c. arvense from invasive range grew faster than c. arvense from native range and the differences are g									
11	ABEL2011B	bromus rubens	United States of N		NA	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	interactions between native species and bromus rubens differ substantially depending on species, a									
12	ABEL2012A	bromus rubens	United States of Y		bromus rubens L. in the mojav	dese	NA	NA	Y	MAP	bromus rubens occupied 55 of the 126 plots (44%) and was present on plots ranging in elevation from								
13	ABEL2012B	bromus rubens	United States of Y		exotic grasses have increased fuel lo	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	this study provides experimental field evidence that native vegetation types exist that may reduce exot									
14	ABEL2012B	schismus arabicus	United States of Y		exotic grasses have increased fuel lo	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	this study provides experimental field evidence that native vegetation types exist that may reduce exot									
15	ABEL2012B	schismus barbatus	United States of Y		exotic grasses have increased fuel lo	NA	NA	Y	COORDS	this study provides experimental field evidence that native vegetation types exist that may reduce exot									
16	ABEL2012C	penisetum ciliare	United States of Y		plant invasions can alter soil proper	NA	NA	Y	MAP	results suggest that [1] soil nutrient status should not be unfavorable for native plant colonization at									
17	ABEL2013A	penisetum ciliare	United States of Y		the species is highly invasive in these	NA	NA	Y	MAP	collectively, these previous studies combined with our results suggest several potential principles re									

Subset of invasive species from GPI database.

SPCIS: Standardized Plant Community with Introduced Status database

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: The database includes comparable information on plant species occurrence, abundance, and native status.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1963 - 2020
- **Spatial:** United States and Puerto Rico

Contact: Lais Petri: petril@umich.edu

Notes: Management, current condition.

Figure:

Distribution of data sources for the Standardized Plant Community with Introduced Status (SPCIS) database.

Catalog of U.S. Federal Early Detection/Rapid Response Invasive Species Databases and Tools: Version 2.0

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: The dataset catalogs and describes existing online, federally supported databases and tools dealing with various aspects of a potential national early detection and rapid response invasive species framework.

Extent

- **Temporal:** variable
- **Spatial:** United States

Contact: Jeffrey T. Morisette (USDA): jeffrey.morisette@usda.gov

Notes: Dataset, early detection and rapid response. User friendly version here: <https://libraryguides.usgs.gov/edrrinvasive>

Figure:

Federal Early Detection/ Rapid Response Invasive Species Resources: Plants & Algae

Search this Guide Search

Overview & Vocabulary All Taxa Aquatic Species Arthropods (Insects) Pathogens & Diseases **Plants & Algae** Non-Species Based Full List

Plants and Algae

Databases

- [Alaska Exotic Plants Information Clearinghouse \(AKEPIC\)](#)
Reporting, mapping application for non-native plant species in Alaska and neighboring Canadian Territories.
[more...](#)
- [Cal-IPC Inventory](#)
Categorizes plants that threaten California's natural areas. The Inventory includes plants that currently cause damage in California (invasive plants) as well as "Watch" plants that are a high risk of becoming invasive in the future.
[more...](#)
- [CalWeedMapper](#)
Tool for mapping invasive plant distribution at the landscape level. Create maps and reports for specific counties or regions.
[more...](#)

Subset of databases included in the EDRR Invasive Species database.

Soil-climate estimates in the western United States: climate averages (1981-2010)

Topics: Climate ▾

Function: Collection of data including soil-climate properties (moisture, temperature, regimes) based on climate normals from 1981-2010.

Extent

- **Temporal:** variable
- **Spatial:** Western US, resolution varies by product

Contact: Michael O'Donnell (USGS): odonnellm@usgs.gov

Notes: Dataset publication: <https://www.mdpi.com/2073-445X/11/10/1856>

Figure:

Figure 6 from [O'Donnell & Manier, 2022](#). (a) shows soil moisture seasonality (in mm) among the four seasons (spring, summer, fall, and winter). (b) shows seasonality within the spring growing season (March, April, May, June).

Modelling species distributions and environmental suitability highlights risk of plant invasions in western US

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: Predictions of the probability of invasive grasses and forbs in the western United States.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** Western US

Contact: Alexandra Urza: alexandra.urza@usda.gov

Notes: Dataset publication: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/ddi.13232>

Figure:

Figure 3 from [McMahon et al., 2021](#). Predicted habitat suitability for grass species. Probability of presence is shown in a range from yellow to red within the model training area for each species, and from blue to red outside the training area, within the Level III ecoregions where the species has been observed. BRJA = *Bromus japonicus*, BRRU2 = *Bromus rubens*, BRTE = *Bromus tectorum*, SCBA = *Schismus barbatus*, TACA8 = *Taeniatherum caput-medusae*, POBU = *Poa bulbosa*.

Rangeland Condition Monitoring Assessment and Projection (RCMAP) Fractional Component Time-Series Across the Western U.S. 1985-2023

Topics: **Invasive Species** **Vegetation Cover**

Function: Fractional cover of rangeland vegetation components (version 6).

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1985 - 2023
- **Spatial:** Western US rangelands

Contact: Matthew Rigge (USGS): mrigge@usgs.gov

Notes: Dataset publication:

<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/15481603.2022.2104786>

Figure:

Figure 2 from [Shi et al., 2022](#). A simplified RCMAP diagram and workflow.

Projections of Rangeland Fractional Component Cover Across the Sagebrush Biome for Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) 4.5 and 8.5 Scenarios for the 2020s, 2050s, and 2080s Time-Periods

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Climate** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾
Future Predictions ▾

Function: Future projections of fractional cover of rangeland vegetation components.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 2020 - 2085
- **Spatial:** Sagebrush biome of the Western US

Contact: Matthew Rigge (USGS): mrigge@usgs.gov

Notes: Dataset publication:

<https://esajournals.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/ecs2.3538>

Figure:

Figure 5 from [Rigge et al., 2021](#). Change in component cover in the 2080s RCP 8.5 scenario relative to the 1985–2018 reference.

Annual herbaceous cover across rangelands of the sagebrush biome

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾ **Vegetation Cover** ▾

Function: Percent cover of all annual herbaceous vegetation.

Extent

- **Temporal:** composite of 2016 - 2018
- **Spatial:** Sagebrush biome of the Western US

Contact: Jeremy Maestas (USGS): jeremy.maestas@usda.gov

Notes: Data are cross-listed on the [Rangeland Analysis Platform](#).

Figure:

Data viewer hosted on the Rangeland Analysis Platform (RAP) partner page.

Database of Invasive Species Lists

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: Watchlists and information on species declared invasive, noxious, prohibited or otherwise harmful.

Extent

- **Temporal:** N/A
- **Spatial:** variable

Contact: National Invasive Species Information Center: invasive@usda.gov

Figure:

Refine Search

Search by keyword

SPECIES LISTS ✕ OHIO ✕

Filter by Subject

Filter by Location

Filter by Source

Sort by: Title (Asc) ▾

Displaying 1 to 4 of 4

[Invasive Plants \(Ohio\)](#)

Ohio Department of Agriculture.

Provides information for plants are designated as invasive in Ohio. No person shall sell, offer for sale, propagate, distribute, import or intentionally cause the dissemination of any invasive plant in Ohio. The invasive plants are first designated by the plant's botanical name and then by the plant's common name.

[Invasive Plants Banned in Ohio](#)

Ohio Invasive Plants Council.

In September of 2014, the Ohio General Assembly granted the Ohio Department of Agriculture (ODA) the exclusive authority to regulate invasive plants species. Under the law invasive plants are defined as plant species that are not native to Ohio whose introduction causes or is likely to cause economic or environmental harm, or harm to human health as determined by scientific studies. After nearly two years of stakeholder outreach, new rules have been established and are effective as of January 7, 2018.

[List of Ohio's Injurious Aquatic Invasive Species \[PDF, 468 KB\]](#)

Ohio Department of Natural Resources.

See also: [Injurious Aquatic Invasive Species](#) for more resources

[Prohibited Noxious Weeds - 901:5-37-01](#)

Ohio Administrative Code.

Invasive species lists for Ohio. The user can select any US state and view lists of their invasive species.

Climate Adaptation Knowledge Exchange Database

Topics: Climate ▾

Function: The Climate Adaptation Knowledge Exchange (CAKE) is an ever-growing knowledge platform that houses a comprehensive digital library of high-quality climate change adaptation resources. We offer a free space for users to find and share open access resources with the larger adaptation community.

Extent

- **Temporal:** varies
- **Spatial:** varies

Contact: info@cakex.org

Figure:

Sample of 168 North Central region resources for climate adaptation planning.

Site Prioritization Tool for Invasive Species

Topics: **Invasive Species** ▾

Function: The Site Prioritization Tool for Invasive Species management is a web-tool that allows users to combine spatial data on factors that may increase invasion risk by non-native species to help efficiently target monitoring and suppression efforts across the conterminous USA.

Extent

- **Temporal:** present
- **Spatial:** CONUS

Contact: Janet Prevy (USGS): jprevey@usgs.gov

Figure:

Spatial invasion risk from burned areas and human transport. Higher risk areas are in red, lower risk areas in blue. Note, the use can up- and down-weight layers using the sliders on the left.

Topics: Future Predictions Climate

Function: A variety of remote sensing climate data tools that process and visualize remote sensing data products. There are also site-specific drought and climate characterization reports available.

Extent

- **Temporal:** 1986 - present
- **Spatial:** CONUS

Contact: climateengine@gmail.com

Figure:

Site report for the BLM Royal Gorge Field Office.

Sagebrush Ecosystem Data Viewer

Topics: **Vegetation Cover** **Invasive Species**

Function: This tool can be used to view and download a variety of USGS and partner datasets pertaining to the sagebrush ecosystem.

Extent

- **Temporal:** variable
- **Spatial:** sagebrush ecosystem (western US)

Contact: Julie Heinrichs (CSU): jheinrx@colostate.edu

Figure:

Probability of cheatgrass invasion layer with the Snake River Plain Management Zone highlighted.